

1 **TCF19 specifies the basal subtype but functions in resistance in hormone receptor-positive breast**
2 **cancer.**

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7 We studied the molecular basis of mechanisms underlying resistance in hormone receptor positive breast
8 cancer by measuring total transcription with next-generation sequencing in human breast cancer cells
9 treated with the active metabolite of the endocrine therapy agent tamoxifen, 4OH-tamoxifen, in
10 charcoal-stripped conditions which mimic endocrine deprivation. The single most up-regulated gene
11 across the entire transcriptome in cells treated with 4OH- tamoxifen in hormone deprived conditions was
12 *TCF19*, a gene we recently identified as the gene whose expression was most transcriptionally activated
13 in the primary tumors of humans with triple negative breast cancer who failed to achieve pathologic
14 complete response (pCR) following treatment with chemotherapy for TNBC. Here we found that *TCF19*
15 was a lineage-specifying homeobox factor in the basal-like subtype, the hormone receptor-negative
16 PAM50 molecular subtype. Interestingly, *TCF19* operated in a proliferation-centered transcriptional
17 network governed by cyclin dependant kinase *CDK2* activity which included spindle-associated *AURKA*,
18 nucleotide synthesis enzymes *RRM2*, proliferation marker *PCNA*, and the major solid tumor transcript
19 *ECT2*. *TCF19* specifies the basal subtype but functions in resistance in hormone receptor-positive breast
20 cancer.
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